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A Case Report

**AGGRESSIVE IGA NEPHROPATHY WITH CRESCENTS AND
NECROTIZING LESIONS IN A 14-YEAR-OLD: A CASE
REPORT OF RAPID PROGRESSION****¹Haider Sarfaraz*, ²Muhammad Abbas, ³Ihtisham Habib, ⁴Malik Hasnat, ⁵Sana Shahab,
⁶Ayesha Zia, ⁷Syed Aftab Ahmad**¹MTI-Lady Reading Hospital Peshawar Pakistan.²MTI-Lady Reading Hospital Peshawar Pakistan.³MTI-Lady Reading Hospital Peshawar Pakistan.⁴MTI-Lady Reading Hospital Peshawar Pakistan.⁵Northwest School of Medicine Peshawar Pakistan.⁶MTI-Lady Reading Hospital Peshawar Pakistan.⁷MTI-Khyber Teaching Hospital Peshawar Pakistan.**Abstract:**

IgA nephropathy (IgAN) stands as the predominant form of primary glomerulonephritis worldwide, exhibiting a wide range of clinical outcomes. In this documented case, we explore the condition through the experience of a 14-year-old girl who faced an aggressive form of IgAN. This particular case was marked by the presence of crescent formations and necrotizing lesions, leading to a series of severe symptoms including nephrotic-range proteinuria, hematuria, noticeable purpuric lesions that could be felt on the skin, abdominal pain, and episodes of hemoptysis.

Upon conducting a renal biopsy, the findings included the presence of crescent formations in 3 out of 25 glomeruli, a necrotizing lesion in one glomerulus, and segmental sclerosis affecting 2 glomeruli. To address these severe manifestations, an early intervention strategy involving corticosteroids, cyclophosphamide, and ACE inhibitors was promptly initiated.

This case emphasizes the critical nature of early detection and the implementation of an aggressive treatment regimen to significantly enhance renal outcomes in children diagnosed with crescentic IgAN (C-IgAN). Furthermore, this analysis search into the pathophysiology behind the condition, its clinical manifestations, and the current therapeutic strategies available for managing such a rare pediatric case. Through this discussion, we aim to shed light on the complexities of IgAN and the importance of a proactive approach in the treatment of this challenging renal disorder.

Keywords: *IgA nephropathy, Nephrotic syndrome, Crescentic IgA nephropathy, Rapidly progressive glomerulonephritis, Proteinuria*

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INTRODUCTION:

First identified by Berger in 1968, IgA nephropathy, also referred to as IgAN, plays a crucial role in the development of glomerulonephritis and renal failure. This condition is marked by the accumulation of IgA antibodies in the mesangial area of the glomeruli. IgA nephropathy stands as a significant factor leading to the advancement of kidney disease, with an estimated 25-30% of those diagnosed progressing to end-stage renal disease within two decades of their initial diagnosis. [1,2]. IgA nephropathy, exhibits a wide range of clinical manifestations. These can include continuous mild microscopic hematuria, possibly accompanied by minor proteinuria while maintaining normal kidney function, extending to cases of nephrotic syndrome. In rare instances, it can progress rapidly, leading to significant loss of kidney function. [3].

Crescentic IgA nephropathy (IgAN) is an uncommon variant marked by the presence of crescents in more than half of the glomeruli, a key component of the kidneys. This particular phenotype is notable for its association with swift progression towards kidney failure. Despite its severity, Crescentic IgAN is relatively rare among those diagnosed with IgA nephropathy. Consequently, it has been the focus of only a limited number of specialized studies, leaving much about this condition yet to be fully understood. [4].

This case report presents a 14-year-old female with rapidly progressive IgAN, highlighting the aggressive nature of C-IgAN and the importance of early therapeutic intervention to preserve renal function.

Case Presentation:

A 14-year-old female presented with a two-month history of erythematous, non-blanchable palpable lesions on her lower limbs extending up to the knees and similar lesions on her upper limbs till the elbows. The patient also complained of abdominal pain, vomiting, hematuria, and one episode of hemoptysis. She developed periorbital edema and bilateral pedal edema during this period. Initially, she was admitted to the dermatology department, but due to her worsening condition and findings of macroalbuminemia on 24-hour urinary protein analysis, she was transferred to the medical ward for further management. After a detailed assessment, she was subsequently referred to the nephrology department for specialist care.

On examination, her vital signs were stable, with a blood pressure of 140/90 mmHg. The physical examination revealed palpable purpura on her limbs and mild abdominal tenderness. No other significant systemic findings were noted. A detailed laboratory workup was conducted. Blood and urine cultures showed no growth after six days and 48 hours of incubation, respectively. An abdominal ultrasound, including the kidneys, ureters, and bladder (KUB), revealed no abnormalities.

A renal biopsy was performed, which showed significant findings. Out of 25 glomeruli examined, three exhibited cellular crescents, and one glomerulus showed necrotizing lesions. Additionally, two glomeruli displayed segmental sclerosis. Mild tubular damage and interstitial inflammation were present, but no evidence of vasculitis, tubular atrophy, or interstitial fibrosis was observed. Immunofluorescence studies revealed granular mesangial deposits of IgA and C3, consistent with crescentic IgA nephropathy (C-IgAN), a severe variant of IgA nephropathy.

Given the severity of the biopsy findings, the patient was immediately started on pulse methylprednisolone therapy followed by oral corticosteroids. Cyclophosphamide was added to her regimen due to the presence of crescents and necrotizing lesions. An ACE inhibitor was also prescribed to manage her proteinuria and maintain blood pressure control. Her renal function remained stable during her hospital stay, and she was discharged with plans for long-term immunosuppressive therapy. Laboratory investigations revealed a total leukocyte count of 11,500/ μ L, hemoglobin of 9.63 g/dL, and a platelet count of 224,000/ μ L. Other notable findings included elevated ESR (50 mm in the first hour), D-dimer (595 ng/mL), low serum albumin (2.8 g/dL), and a 24-hour urinary protein excretion of 12,276 mg, indicating significant proteinuria. Despite the severity of her renal pathology, the patient's renal function remained preserved with a serum creatinine level of 0.36 mg/dL. Her long-term prognosis will depend on her response to ongoing immunosuppressive therapy and control of proteinuria. Regular follow-ups have been arranged to monitor her renal function, proteinuria, and overall clinical progress.

Figure 1 : Histopathology slide showing **crescents in glomerulus** (white arrow)

Figure 2 : Histopathology slide showing **Necrotizing segmental lesion of capillary wall in glomeruli** (white arrow)

TABLE 1: Basic lab investigations

Parameter	Value	Reference range
Total Leukocyte Count	11500/ul	4000-11000/ul
Hemoglobin	9.63g/dl	11.5-17.5 g/dl
Platelets	224000/ul	150000-450000/ul
MCV	76.9 fl	76-96 fl
HbsAg(By ICT)	Negative	Negative
Anti HCV (By ICT)	Negative	Negative
Anti HIV (By ICT)	Negative	Negative
Serum Creatinine	0.36 mg /dl	0.3-0.9 mg/dl
BUN	20.45 mg/dl	18-45 mg/dl
Serum Albumin	2.8 g/dl	3.5-5.5 g/dl
Serum Calcium	7.8 mg/dl	8.0-10 mg/dl
Total Bilirubin	0.2 mg/dl	0.1-1.0 mg/dl
ALT	30 U/L	10-50 U/L
ALP	101 U/L	>187 U/L
ESR	50 mm / 1 st hour	0-20 mm /1 st hour
CRP	<0.4 mg/dl	<1.0 mg/dl
D-Dimer	595ng/ml	Upto 200
Serum Ferritin	21ng/ml	13-150
Cholesterol	178 mg/dl	<200 mg/dl
Triglycerides	237 mg /dl	<200 mg/dl
HDL Cholesterol	45 mg/dl	35-65 mg/dl
LDL Cholesterol	98 mg/dl	<150 mg/dl
PT	12 Seconds	12 -15 Seconds
INR	1	0.9-1.1
aPTT	33 Seconds	29-43 Seconds
ASO	Negative	Negative
ACR	3726 mg/g	Normal <30 mg/g

ALT: Alanine Transaminase; ALP: Alkaline Phosphatase; ESR: Erythrocyte Sedimentation Rate; HCV: Hepatitis C Virus; HbsAg: Hepatitis B Surface Antigen; MCV: Mean Corpuscular Volume; HIV: Human Immunodeficiency Virus; BUN: Blood Urea Nitrogen; CRP: C-Reactive Protein; ACR: Albumin-to-Creatinine Ratio; ASO: Anti-Streptolysin O

TABLE 2: Routine urine exam

Urine R.E	Value	Reference Range
Colour	Yellow	Yellow
Appearance	Clear	Clear
Glucose	Nil	Negative
pH	8.0	4.5-8.0
Protein	Positive(+)	Negative
PUS/WBC	10-15	0-5/HPF
RBC	Numerous	0-5/HPF
Epithelial Cells	Positive(+)	0-10/HPF
Hyaline Cast	Negative (-)	0-4/HPF
Granular Cast	Negative (-)	0/HPF
Amorphous Urates	Nil	Nil
Amorphous Phosphate	Positive(+)	Nil

RBC : Red Blood Cells ; WBC : White Blood Cells ; HPF: High-powered field ; R.E : routine examination

TABLE 3: 24 hours urinary protein

Protein- 24 Hours Urine	Value	Reference Range
Volume	2000ml	1500-2000 ml
24 Hours Urinary Protein	12276 mg/ 24 hours	< 150 mg/ 24 hours

DISCUSSION:

Crescentic IgA nephropathy stands as an infrequent yet severe subtype of IgAN [4]. The presence of a glomerular crescent signifies the rupture of glomerular capillaries, often due to a vigorous immune response marked by cytotoxic elements such as the complement membrane attack complex and extracellular histones, leading to necroinflammation. This results in the leakage of coagulation factors and the formation of fibrin within Bowman's space, which lacks platelets and other blood clot components, prompting the hyperplasia of parietal epithelial cells and the formation of crescents. These crescents contribute to the decline of single nephron GFR by either increasing counter pressure and causing the collapse of the glomerular tuft or by blocking tubular outflow. Features such as fibrotic changes, infiltration of immune cells around the glomeruli, rupture of Bowman's capsule, and influx of immune cells are variable outcomes of crescent formation, making them less ideal targets for therapy [5]. In this particular case, renal biopsy uncovered crescents in 12% of glomeruli along with necrotizing lesions, pointing to extensive glomerular damage.

The prognosis of IgAN heavily relies on histopathological findings, like those observed in this instance. The disease's progression is gauged using the Oxford MEST-C score, which evaluates five factors: mesangial (M) and endocapillary hypercellularity (E), segmental sclerosis (S), tubulointerstitial fibrosis/tubular atrophy (T), and the presence of crescents (C) [6]. This scoring system allows for the

categorization of patients into risk levels. Histopathological insights offer critical prognostic information at diagnosis [7]. For this case, an M1E1S1T0C1 score highlighted a high activity level of the disease and a significant risk of progression [8]. The primary strategy for managing proteinuria and reducing blood pressure in patients with IgAN often involves the use of angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitors or angiotensin receptor blockers (ARBs), aiming for a blood pressure target of 130/80 mm Hg. If proteinuria exceeds 1 g/d, the goal for systolic blood pressure is set below 125 mm Hg [1]. In this scenario, initiating treatment with an ACE inhibitor effectively controlled proteinuria, and the patient showed a positive response to the initial therapy. Patients exhibiting recurrent macroscopic hematuria or isolated microscopic hematuria with proteinuria under 1 g/24 h may not require specific intervention. Those with nephrotic syndrome and minimal changes upon renal biopsy are treated as cases of minimal change nephropathy. Currently, there's a lack of evidence supporting corticosteroid use for treating nephrotic IgAN outside these patient groups. Those presenting with acute renal failure are assessed to differentiate between acute tubular necrosis, which only requires supportive care, and crescentic IgAN, where a treatment regimen akin to that for renal small vessel vasculitis involving cyclophosphamide and corticosteroids is recommended in the absence of significant chronic histological damage. Patients facing the highest risk of progressive renal impairment include those with hypertension, proteinuria exceeding 1 g/24 h, and a

diminished glomerular filtration rate at diagnosis [2]. Corticosteroid therapy has been shown to decelerate the reduction in glomerular filtration rate, diminish proteinuria, and avert kidney failure in high-risk IgAN patients who have undergone maximal supportive care for a minimum of 3 months. Present treatment protocols suggest considering a 6-month corticosteroid therapy for patients who continue to experience proteinuria greater than 1 g/day despite 3 months of intensive RAAS blockade [9]. For cases of crescentic IgAN affecting over 10% of glomeruli with active glomerular inflammation and deteriorating renal function without significant chronic damage [2], immunosuppressive therapy with cyclophosphamide and corticosteroids is advised.

Current KDIGO guidelines advocate for the early detection and commencement of supportive care treatments, prioritizing the use of antihypertensives that inhibit RAAS over corticosteroid therapy to slow the transition to CKD and ESRD [10]. This case emphasizes the need for meticulous monitoring and ongoing follow-up in pediatric IgAN patients, especially those exhibiting severe histopathological characteristics such as crescents and necrotizing lesions.

CONCLUSION:

This case report describes a pediatric patient with aggressive crescentic IgA nephropathy, characterized by rapid disease progression and severe renal pathology. Early diagnosis and prompt initiation of immunosuppressive therapy, including corticosteroids and cyclophosphamide, were critical in managing the disease and preventing further renal deterioration. Pediatric C-IgAN is rare, but it poses significant challenges due to its rapid progression and poor prognosis. Close monitoring, aggressive treatment, and ongoing research into novel therapies are essential for improving outcomes in these patients.

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